

Combining Feature Selection and Deep Learning for Precise COVID-19 Cases Forecasting: A Hybrid Approach

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Abstract- Accurately predicting the number of new COVID-19 cases is crucial for informing public health policy and resource allocation decisions. In this study, we propose a hybrid approach for COVID-19 cases prediction using Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) for feature selection with Optuna hyperparameter tuning and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). We use a multivariate time series dataset consisting of variables related to COVID-19 in India. We use LightGBM for feature selection and the selected features are used as input to the LSTM model. We use Optuna to tune the hyperparameters of LightGBM and evaluate the performance of our hybrid model using metrics like mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and r-squared score (R^2). Our experimental results show that our hybrid model outperforms both LSTM and LightGBM models individually and other similar combinations of feature selector algorithm and predictor models in terms of prediction accuracy. Specifically, our hybrid model achieves a MAPE of 0.87 on the test dataset. The selected features also provide insights into the most relevant factors for predicting COVID-19 cases in India.

Keywords- LSTM, LightGBM, COVID-19, Feature Selection, Forecasting, Healthcare.

1. INTRODUCTION

A pandemic named novel coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) was first reported in Wuhan, China in 2019 and subsequently spread exponentially. Most coronaviruses aren't harmful; they're just a type of common illness that affects your nose, sinuses, or upper throat. SARS-CoV-2 is the virus that causes COVID-19, a condition that can lead to a respiratory infection. Patients with COVID-19 infection may experience a variety of symptoms, and these symptoms may change over time. Those who breathe air contaminated by droplets and other small airborne particles carrying the infection are the main carriers of COVID-19. When an infected person speaks, breathes, coughs, sneezes, or sings, those patches are exhaled. The closer people are to one another, the higher the likelihood of transmission. Yet, the virus can spread further, especially outside. The sanctioned names COVID - 19 and SARS-CoV-2 were issued by the WHO on 11 February 2020. People with COVID-19 infection may have different symptoms, and their symptoms may change over time. People contract COVID-19 most often via breathing air contaminated by droplets and tiny airborne particles carrying the infection. As they breathe, talk, cough, sneeze, or sing, infected persons exhale those patches. The closer someone is to you, the greater the chance of transmission. Treatment for COVID-19 depends on the strictness of the infection. For milder ails, resting at home and taking medicine to reduce fever is constantly sufficient. More severe cases may bear hospitalization, with treatment that might include intravenous specifics, supplemental oxygen, supported ventilation and other supportive measures. To attack the epidemic, strict measures were put in place around the world. In March, travel restrictions and recommendations for basic handwashing techniques went into effect.

Yet, it was anticipated that these precautions would only slow the development of the disease; scientists realized that a vaccine would be necessary to end the epidemic. The COVID - 19 vaccines are considerably credited for their part in reducing the spread of COVID - 19 and reducing the strictness and death caused by COVID - 19. Especially, there was a race across countries in developing a successful vaccine that could cure the complaint. ultimate of the biotechnical industriousness bloomed during the epidemic times. Several small-scale industries incurred heavy losses due to consecutive lockdowns. The quotidian life of every existent changed in these times. utmost fields like education and IT companies have shifted to online modes. On the other hand, a variety of forecasting techniques are used to forecast how many COVID-19 cases will be reported in the next day or month. These predictions are used to take precautionary measures in the region like administering lockdowns in that regions where there is a high spread rate and administering flight bans from countries where there is a hike in COVID-19 contagion spread. Also, to overcome the deficiency of medical needs in the forthcoming days there is a need for accurate predictions. Various ways and algorithms are used in the process of predicting COVID-19 cases. The machine algorithms are used considerably in several COVID-19 predictions. Also, Artificial Intelligence is used in several medical operations. Therefore, estimating the number of

positive instances in the upcoming days solely based on historical data is not a reliable forecasting method. For public health experts and politicians to make educated decisions on resource allocation, healthcare planning, and containment tactics, it is essential to accurately estimate the spread of COVID-19. Our paper offers a thorough review of the deep learning model's performance in predicting COVID-19, including its capacity to reflect the pandemic's complex and dynamic nature. Additionally, we use methods for feature selection and hyperparameter optimization to enhance the performance of our model. The study uses COVID-19 data taken from India. The results can help decision-makers make informed policy decisions, allocate resources, and prepare healthcare systems for the anticipated number of cases.

2. RELATED WORKS

Since the spread of COVID-19 is a challenge for all forms of departments, it became the worst pandemic of this century. The jobs of all fields are highly affected by this widespread and there is a need for an immediate solution. Researchers and scientists worldwide carried out various scientific experiments to identify the reasons for the disease and tried to find a mitigation plan.

Several researchers had defined a solution for the above problem. The time series forecasting method is used for prediction models. Tiwari et al. put forth a model using Covid-19 spread patterns in China to predict the Covid-19 spread pattern in India.[1] But densely populated countries' epidemic spread patterns are different from other countries. Several AI techniques and models are used to help the national authorities to take proper countermeasures. This model uses the WEKA tool for machine-learning purposes. Similarly, Villavicencio et al. utilized several ML algorithms in developing a model to predict COVID-19 cases through WEKA machine learning software.[2] On other hand, Kucharski et al. did a SARS-CoV2 transmission model from several existing datasets to predict the nature of the COVID-19 spread among Wuhan and its neighbouring cities.[3] Tuli et al. have predicted the growth trend of COVID-19 and compared the results with the Gaussian model. The prediction model is deployed using the FogBus framework for accurate prediction. It outperforms the Robust Weibull fitting model.[4]

Using the data from Italy, Zhao et al. have used the BP neural network algorithm to analyze and predict the development trend of COVID-19.[5] The fitting value of the model is compared with the real value, and the fitting degree reaches 0.99. Bharathi et al. has constructed and created a trained artificial neural network that can predict COVID-19 in patients without symptoms and be utilized for conditioning monitoring in COVID-affected patients.[6] They have used the MATLAB Neural Network toolbox in their work. Ardabili et al. use a grey wolf optimizer-integrated artificial neural network for COVID-19 outbreak forecasts by using the Global dataset.[7] A robust hybrid Artificial Neural Network integrated by Grey Wolf Optimizer (ANN-GWO). With high accuracy, this GWO has been selected as the best prediction model for global COVID-19 prediction. Cheng et al. proposed the ARIMA-SVM integration model by using the global cumulative number of confirmed cases. The combined model of ARIMA and SVM has reduced the average absolute error percentage. [8]

Gupta et al. performed forecasting of all classes using a random forest model which outperformed the other ML Algorithms and used it for the prediction and analysis of COVID-19 data. Random forest model for multi-class classification.[9] K-fold cross-validation is performed to measure the consistency. Tahir et al. attempted to forecast COVID-19 via Registration Slips of Patients using ResNet-101 and Performance Analysis and Comparison of Prediction for COVID-19 using Faster R-CNN, Mask R-CNN, and ResNet-50 in two dimensions.[10] Deb and Majumdar have proposed a time series methodology to examine incidence patterns and calculate the COVID-19 reproduction rate. [11] Where information on total or partial lockout was available, it was incorporated into the model. As a result, the model is brief and demonstrates that a time-dependent quadratic trend successfully represents the disease's incidence pattern. Vaishya et al. mentioned that by gathering and analyzing all historical data, AI technology plays a crucial part in detecting the cluster of cases and aids in predicting where this virus would influence in the future.[12] Furthermore, it has the potential to improve the planning, treatment and reported outcomes of the COVID-19 patient, being an evidence-based medical tool. Iqbal et al. used long short-term memory (LSTM) to predict the volume of COVID-19 patients in Pakistan and the results revealed that the predicted patient count of the proposed model is much closer to the actual patient count. [13].

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1. System Design of Proposed Methodology

3.1 Data Collection and Transformation

Data is collected from the COVID-19 Open Data Web portal of Google. This portal has COVID-19 data from the beginning of the virus spread to 15 September 2022. This portal data is from several official websites including the Indian government's website. It contains the state-wise and country-wise infection data. We are using only data from Indian states. A hybrid predictive model is built using LightGBM and LSTM. The system design can be seen in Fig. 1 for the COVID-19 cases prediction. First, the important features are extracted using LightGBM and a subset of data with specific columns is used as input for LSTM. The LSTM model is trained using the temporal COVID-19 data available in India. For training the data in the model, the data must be preprocessed (i.e.) the data must be time series data. We are using the Time-Series Generator Module provided by Keras to get time series data. This data is divided into two partitions: training data and testing data. Now, it can fit into the LSTM model. The training data is stored in batches and used in the training phase whereas the testing data is used in the testing phase. The data is label encoded using LabelEncoder and normalized using MinMaxScaler.

3.2 LightGBM Model

LightGBM (Light Gradient Boosting Machine) is a powerful and efficient gradient-boosting framework that can be used for both regression and classification tasks. It is based on the Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT) algorithm and uses a novel technique called Gradient-based One-Side Sampling (GOSS) to speed up training and reduce memory usage. The LightGBM algorithm works by iteratively adding new decision trees to the model, with each tree attempting to correct the errors made by the previous trees. The algorithm starts by building a single decision tree that predicts the target variable based on the input features. The output of this tree is then used as the initial predictions for the model. At each iteration, the algorithm adds a new decision tree to the model and updates the predictions by adding the output of the new tree to the previous predictions. The new tree is built to minimize the residual error between the predicted values and the actual values in the training data. Until a stopping requirement is satisfied, such as a maximum number of iterations or a minimal performance gain, the training process is continued. The decision trees are added together to form the final model, and the weights are based on the learning rate and the number of iterations. The LightGBM algorithm is designed to handle large-scale datasets with high-dimensional features and is optimized for both accuracy and speed. It is one of the most popular machine learning algorithms used in industry today, especially in the fields of natural language processing, computer vision, and speech recognition. The LightGBM algorithm uses the following formulas to compute:

3.3.1 The gradient and hessian of the loss function:

Gradient:

$$g_i = \frac{\partial L(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)}$$

Hessian

$$h_i = \frac{\partial^2 L(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)^2}$$

y_i : The actual (ground truth) value of the target variable for the i -th sample in the dataset.

$F(x_i)$: The predicted value of the target variable for the i -th sample, given the features x_i

$L(y_i, F(x_i))$: The loss function that quantifies the difference between the actual and predicted values for the i -th sample.

3.3.2 Objective function:

The objective function in LightGBM is used to measure the quality of the model. It is typically a loss function that quantifies the difference between predicted and actual values. We have used the mean absolute error (MAE).

$$\text{MAE} = \sum_{i=1}^D |x_i - y_i|$$

D : The total number of samples in the dataset.

$|x_i - y_i|$: The absolute difference between the actual and predicted values for the i -th sample.

3.3.3 Gradient-based One-Side Sampling (GOSS)

i. Calculate the gradients for each sample:

$$G_i = \frac{\partial L(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)}$$

ii. Sort the samples based on their gradients, and select the top $r\%$ samples:

$$\text{top } r = i: G_i \geq G(1 - r)\%$$

iii. Use only the selected samples for training the tree.

3.3.4 Leaf-wise growth split finding:

The split finding algorithm in LightGBM is used to determine the best way to split a node in a decision tree. It is based on the gain of the split, which is defined as the reduction in the objective function achieved by splitting the node. The gain of a split can be computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Gain} = 0.5 \cdot \frac{(\sum_{i \in \text{left}} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in \text{left}} h_i + \lambda} + 0.5 \cdot \frac{(\sum_{i \in \text{right}} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in \text{right}} h_i + \lambda} - \frac{(\sum_{i \in \text{left}} g_i + \sum_{i \in \text{right}} g_i)^2}{\sum_{i \in \text{left}} h_i + \sum_{i \in \text{right}} h_i + \lambda}$$

left: the subset of data samples that go to the left child node

right: the subset of data samples that go to the right child node

g_i : the gradient of the loss function for the i -th sample

h_i : the Hessian of the loss function for the i -th sample

λ : the regularization term, which is a hyperparameter that controls the complexity of the tree model

3.3.5 Histogram-based algorithm for splitting nodes:

Instead of sorting the data at each node, the data is first binned into discrete intervals, and then the algorithm uses a histogram to compute the best split point.

3.3.6 Leaf output calculation:

The leaf output calculation in LightGBM is used to compute the output value for each leaf node in the decision tree. The output value is typically the average of the target values for the samples in the leaf node. It can be computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Output} = - \frac{\sum_{i \in \text{node}} g_i}{\sum_{i \in \text{node}} h_i + \lambda}$$

node: the subset of data samples that belong to the leaf node

g_i : the gradient of the loss function for the i -th sample

h_i : the Hessian of the loss function for the i -th sample

λ : the regularization term, which is a hyperparameter that controls the complexity of the tree model

3.3.7 Exclusive Feature Bundling (EFB):

1. For each feature i :

- a. For each feature j such that $j > i$:
- i. Calculate the correlation coefficient $\rho_{i,j}$ between feature i and feature j using the Pearson correlation formula.

$$\rho_{i,j} = \frac{\text{cov}(x_i, x_j)}{\sigma_{x_i} \sigma_{x_j}}$$

$\rho_{i,j}$ is the correlation coefficient between features i and j

$\text{cov}(x_i, x_j)$ is the covariance between x_i and x_j

σ_{x_i} and σ_{x_j} are the standard deviations of x_i and x_j

- ii. If $\rho_{i,j}$ is greater than a specified threshold τ , combine features i and j into a single feature and add it to the list of bundled features.

2. Replace the original features with the bundled features and train the model using the bundled features.

3.3.8 Gradient-based Decision Tree - Feature Importance (GBDT-FI):

To calculate the relative importance of each feature based on its contribution to the gradient-boosting process:

$$FI_j = \frac{1}{T} \sum_t 1^T \text{gain}_t \cdot I(f_j \in T_t)$$

FI_j is the importance of feature j ,

T is the total number of trees,

gain_t is the gain of tree t

T_t is the set of leaves in tree t ,

$I(f_j \in T_t)$ is an indicator function that is 1 if feature j appears in tree t , and 0 otherwise.

We have used hyper-parametric tuning using the optuna module from the verstack package in Python. Optuna is a Python library for hyperparameter optimization that can be used to optimize the hyperparameters of LightGBM. Hyperparameters are parameters that are set before training a machine learning model and affect its performance. Optimizing hyperparameters can improve the performance of the model. LightGBM when combined with optuna gives the best performance. Since, LightGBM is one of the fastest gradient-boosting machine learning algorithms whereas Optuna is the quickest hyperparametric tuning framework. This combination is available as an open-source framework in Python. The LightGBM is used to find the feature importance of all the features that impact the spread rate of COVID-19. And from that, the parameters that affect the COVID-19 transmission is extracted to form new data which is used as the input data for the LSTM model. Also, the dimensionality reduction is carried out in this phase.

Algorithm 1: LightGBM for Feature Selection

1. Initialize the data, hyperparameters, and tree ensemble parameters.
 - D : Training data with N samples, X and target values y
 - Hyperparameters: `num_trees`, `learning_rate`, `max_depth`, `min_split_gain`, `min_data_in_leaf`, `lambda`, `feature_fraction`, `bagging_fraction`
 - Tree ensemble parameters: $F = \emptyset, i = 1$
2. Build the initial decision tree.
 - T_i is a binary tree of depth `max_depth`
 - It has $2^{\text{max_depth}} - 1$ leaves
 - Let N_i be the set of samples assigned to leaf i
3. For i in $1, \dots, \text{num_trees}$:
 1. Compute the gradients and Hessians for each sample j in D .
 - a. $g_j = \frac{\partial L(y_j, F_{i-1}(X_j))}{\partial F_{i-1}(X_j)}$
 - b. $h_j = \frac{\partial^2 L(y_j, F_{i-1}(X_j))}{\partial F_{i-1}(X_j)^2}$
 2. Split the leaves of T_i to create $2^{\text{max_depth}} - 1$ new leaves using a greedy algorithm to maximize the split gain, G .
 - a. $G = \text{Gain} - \text{gamma}$
 - b. $\text{Gain} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(\sum_{j \in L} g_j)^2}{\sum_{j \in L} h_j + \lambda} + \frac{(\sum_{j \in R} g_j)^2}{\sum_{j \in R} h_j + \lambda} \right) - \frac{(\sum_{j \in N_i} g_j)^2}{\sum_{j \in N_i} h_j + \lambda}$

- c. Exclusive Feature Bundling: Use only a subset of the features for each split
 - d. Max Feature Usage: Limit the maximum number of times a feature can be used
 - e. Min Data in Leaf: Ensure that each leaf has at least min_data_in_leaf samples
 - f. Min Split Gain: Ensure that the gain from each split is at least min_split_gain
3. Compute the optimal output for each leaf in T_i .

$$Output_j = \frac{\sum_{j \in N_i} g_j}{\sum_{j \in N_i} h_j + \lambda}$$

- 4. Add the new decision tree T_i to the ensemble F .
 - a. $F_i = T_i$
 - b. $F = F \cup F_i$
- 4. Compute the feature importance of each feature in X based on its number of splits across all trees in F .

$$I_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{num_trees} \mathbb{I}_{j \in Split T_i}}{num_trees}$$

Where $\mathbb{I}_{j \in Split T_i}$ is an indicator function that is 1 if feature j is used to split any leaf in T_i , and 0 otherwise.

- 5. Update the predictions of the ensemble F .
- 6. Train model F to make predictions on new data X_{new} . The prediction for a single sample x_{new} is given by:

$$\hat{y}_{new} = F(X_{new}) = \sum_{i=1}^{num_trees} learning_rate \cdot F_i(X_{new})$$

3.3 LSTM Model

LSTM is a type of Recurrent Neural Network used to learn, process, and classify sequential data because these networks can learn long-term dependencies between time steps of data especially for classification and regression tasks. The amount of time needed for training depends on the number of nodes. An input layer, a number of hidden layers, and an output layer are all features of the LSTM model. The required output is created using an activation function. This article uses a rectified linear activation function as its activation function. We employ the Root Mean Squared Propagation (RMSProp) Optimizer after the model has been constructed. The training is continued until the specified number of epochs have been reached or until the early stopping condition, which includes the convergence and value loss monitor conditions, is met.

The sequential model is created from the Keras module, and then numerous LSTM layers are added with different numbers of neurons in each layer, including hidden layers and ultimately a dense layer. The dropout rate in this model serves as a safeguard against overfitting. For estimating the patient count, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MSE) loss function is used. After the predictions are made, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error is the statistic utilized to build the LSTM Layer.

Fig. 2. Architecture Diagram of LSTM Network

3.3.1 Input Gate Layer

The initial step is to determine what new information to store in the cell state. A sigmoid activation function is applied to the concatenated output of the previous hidden state and the current input to determine which values to update. A tanh activation function is also applied to the concatenated output to generate a new vector of candidate values to add to the cell state.

$$\begin{aligned} i_t &= \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \\ \tilde{C}_t &= \tanh(W_c \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c) \\ c_t &= i_t \cdot \tilde{C}_t \end{aligned} \quad \dots (1)$$

3.3.2 Forget Gate Layer:

Choosing which data to delete from the prior cell state is the next step. The output of the previous hidden state and the current input are combined, and a sigmoid activation function is used to provide a value between 0 and 1 for each component of the cell state. The amount of data from the cell state that should be retained or discarded is represented by this value.

$$\begin{aligned} f_t &= \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \\ c_{t-1} &= c_t \cdot f_t \end{aligned}$$

3.3.3 Update Cell State:

The next step is to update the cell state by combining the previous cell state with the candidate values determined. The previous cell state is multiplied elementwise by the output of the forget gate layer to discard unnecessary information, and the output of the input gate layer is multiplied elementwise with the candidate values to add new information to the cell state.

$$c_t = f_t \cdot c_{t-1} + i_t \cdot \tilde{C}_t$$

3.3.4 Output Gate Layer:

The final step is to determine the output of the LSTM cell. A sigmoid activation function is applied to the concatenated output of the previous hidden state and the current input to determine which values to output. A tanh activation function is also applied to the updated cell state to generate a vector of candidate output values. The output of the output gate layer is multiplied elementwise with the candidate values to produce the final output of the LSTM cell.

$$\begin{aligned} o_t &= \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \\ h_t &= o_t \cdot \tanh(c_t) \end{aligned}$$

3.3.5 Loss Function:

MSE (Mean Squared Error) is a common loss function used in machine learning and deep learning, including in LSTM models. It measures the average squared difference between the predicted and actual values. In the context of an LSTM, the predicted values are the outputs of the model, which are compared to the actual values of the time series. The MSE loss function computes the average of the squared differences between the predicted and actual values across all time steps in the sequence.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2$$

y_t represents the actual value at time step t ,

$\hat{y}_t$ represents the predicted value at time step t ,

n is the total number of time steps in the sequence.

3.3.6 Optimizer:

An optimizer in LSTM networks is a particular method that is used during training to change the network's weights and biases to reduce the loss function. The optimizer oversees changing the model's parameters in response to discrepancies between expected and actual results. With RMSprop, the learning rate for each weight is modified depending on the root mean square (RMS) of recent gradients. Based on the size of recent gradients, RMSprop adaptively modifies the learning rate for each weight, which can enhance convergence and reduce oscillations during training.

$$v_t = \rho v_{t-1} + (1 - \rho) g_t^2$$

v_t is the moving average of the squared gradients

g_t is the gradient at iteration t ,

ρ is a hyperparameter called the decay rate, typically set to 0.9.

The update rule for each weight w_t is then given by:

$$w_t = w_{t-1} - \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{s_t + \epsilon}} \cdot g_t$$

w_t is the weight at time t ,
 η is the learning rate,
 g_t is the gradient at time t ,
 v_t is the exponentially weighted moving average of the squared gradient at time t
 ϵ is a small constant to avoid division by zero.

3.3.7 Activation Function:

An activation function is a mathematical function that is applied to the output of each LSTM unit in a neural network to introduce non-linearity. In an LSTM, the activation function is typically applied to the output of the cell state and the output gate. The tanh function is a non-linear function that squashes the input value to the range of -1 to 1. The tanh function is a popular choice due to its ability to introduce non-linearity while also being differentiable and suitable for gradient-based optimization.

$$\tanh(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}}$$

Fig. 3. Architecture Diagram of LSTM Cell

Algorithm 2: LSTM for COVID-19 Cases Prediction

Input: Dataset with Feature Selected from LightGBM

Output: Predicted new confirmed cases

Globals: G : TimeSeriesGenerator()

$split()$: TrainTestSplit()

N : LSTM Network

E : Number of epochs

$D \leftarrow read(data)$

$traindata, testdata \leftarrow split(D)$

$K \leftarrow G(traindata)$

$L \leftarrow G(testdata)$

for $k = 1$ to E **do**

 Train(N, K);

end for

$P \leftarrow predictions(N, L)$

MAPE($testdata, P$)

Graph($testdata, P$)

Here after the prediction is completed the evaluation metrics like MAPE and R^2 are done to check the performance of the model with the test data. MAPE stands for Mean Absolute Percentage Error, and it is a commonly used metric for evaluating the accuracy of forecasts or predictions. It measures the average percentage difference between actual and predicted values, relative to the actual values. The formula for MAPE is

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{A_i - F_i}{A_i} \right|$$

A_i is the actual value,
 F_i is the forecasted value,
 n is the number of observations.

A statistical measure known as the coefficient of determination, abbreviated R^2 , shows how much of the variance for a dependent variable in a regression model is explained by one or more independent variables. It has a value between 0 and 1, with 0 denoting that the model explains no variance in the dependent variable and 1 denoting that the model fully explains the dependent variable's variance. The formula for R^2 (r-squared)

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$$

n : The total number of observations.

y_i : The observed value of the dependent variable y for the i -th observation.

$\bar{y}$: The mean value of the dependent variable y across all the observations.

$\hat{y}_i$: The predicted value of the dependent variable y for the i -th observation, based on the independent variables x and the estimated coefficients.

The performance metrics above are cross validated with the percentage difference between the actual cases and predicted cases we get from the models. This is very efficient form of evaluation since each and every confirmed case has a bigger economic aspect. In other words, the lesser the percentage difference the greater the efficiency of the model. The formula for percentage difference of cases is

$$D = \frac{|n_1 - n_2|}{\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2}} \times 100$$

n_1 : the actual cases

n_2 : the predicted cases by a model

Finally, the predicted data is visualized using multiple graphs for better understanding. The training data contains 80% of the data and testing data contains 20% data. The optimization technique is used. Then the data is trained with the different number of batches and epochs. After training, the prediction is made. The accuracy value is found from the predicted values and tested values. Finally, the results are graphically represented.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The data for COVID-19 Cases Prediction is taken from the Google Health Repository of India. The first phase is feature importance and selection, and the second phase is prediction. The models used for feature importance and selection are CatBoost, XGBoost, and LightGBM, while for prediction, Bi-LSTM, GRU, and LSTM have been used. The comparison is made between these models to understand which model performs better in each phase.

4.1.1 Feature Importance and Selection Phase:

In this phase, the goal is to select the most important features that have a high impact on the prediction accuracy. The three models used for this phase are CatBoost, XGBoost, and LightGBM. These models are gradient boosting decision trees that work by iteratively adding trees to the model while minimizing the loss function.

CatBoost is a machine learning library that is used for both classification and regression tasks. It is known for its ability to handle categorical variables without requiring any pre-processing. XGBoost(Extreme Gradient Boosting) is another gradient boosting decision tree-based ensemble learning method that sequentially builds multiple weak models to improve the overall predictive power of the model. LightGBM is a fast and efficient gradient boosting decision tree algorithm that is designed to work with large datasets.

The comparison between these models for feature importance and selection involves evaluating each model's ability to select the most important features and rank them in order of importance. The model that can identify the most important features accurately will perform better in this phase.

Fig. 4. Feature Importance and Selection using XGBoost

Fig. 5. Feature Importance and Selection using CatBoost

Fig. 6. Feature Importance and Selection using LightGBM

Fig. 7.

4.1.2 Prediction Phase:

In this phase, the goal is to predict the output variable based on the selected features. The three models used for this phase are Bi-LSTM, GRU, and LSTM. These models are all variants of recurrent neural networks that are widely used for sequence prediction tasks.

LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) is a type of recurrent neural network that is used for sequence prediction tasks. It has the ability to remember previous input values and produce output values based on the current input and previous inputs. Bi-LSTM (Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory) is an extension of LSTM that works in both forward and backward directions. GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) is another variant of LSTM that is designed to be simpler than LSTM and works well on smaller datasets.

Fig. 8. Prediction using the Features Selected from CatBoost

	CatBoost		
	MAPE	R ²	Accuracy
Bi-LSTM	3.78	<0	96.21
GRU	3.77	<0	96.23
LSTM	2.80	<0	97.19

Table 1. Accuracy of Predictions of CatBoost

XGBoost		
MAPE	R ²	Accuracy

Bi- LSTM	9.90	<0	90.10
GRU	8.56	<0	91.43
LSTM	10.16	<0	89.83

Table 2. Accuracy of Predictions of XGBoost

Fig. 9. Prediction using the Features Selected from XGBoost

LightGBM			
	MAPE	R ²	Accuracy
Bi- LSTM	1.02	0.53	98.98
GRU	1.06	0.45	98.94
LSTM	0.87	0.66	99.13

Fig. 10. Prediction using the Features Selected from LightGBM

Table 3. Accuracy of Predictions of LightGBM

Model	Performance Metrics			
	MAPE	R ²	Accuracy	% Difference
LSTM	2.07	0.16	97.92	46.20
LightGBM - LSTM	0.87	0.66	99.13	0.90

Table 4. Comparison with State of Art approach

Fig 10. Comparison with State of Art Approach

The comparison between these models for prediction involves evaluating each model's ability to predict the output variable accurately. The model that can predict the output variable with the highest accuracy will perform better in this phase. The pie-chart comparison in the feature selection phase tells that the distribution of feature importance is better in LightGBM than in XGBoost and CatBoost. The latter algorithm concentrates on some of the features and give more importance to some features. But the former one has unique methodologies like GOSS and EFB which proves to be the best in giving the feature impotance.

The Table 4 depicts that the accuracy we get with only the LSTM and from the proposed LightGBM-LSTM model. This proves the efficieny of the hybrid model is better than the model with predictio phase only. The proposed hybrid model extracts the features which has highest impact on the confirmed cases. Table 5 contains the performance in terms of MAPE, R^2 and accuracy. There are totally 9 combinations of hybrid models taken into comparison table and their performace is evaluated. Also, the different are combinations are worked with different number of features. Finally, we can conclude from the accuracy column that the LightGBM-LSTM model gives the highest accuracy of 99.13 with 15 features. The XGBoost didn't do well with this dataset since most of the R^2 error values is less that zero which means the features it selected don't do well with the model. CatBoost gave better features when compared to XGBoost based on R^2 and Accuracy. But, LightGBM outperforms the other gradient boosting models and gave the best performance with LSTM.

The Table 6 gives a deeper insight about the performance of the models in terms of percentage difference calculated between the actual cases between March 1, 2022 to September 19, 2022 and the cases predicted by the hybrid models. The LightGBM-LSTM models gives the best COVID-19 cases with the feature count of 10, 15, 20 and 25. Using 5 features, CatBoost-BiLSTM model gives a better result. But the results clearly proves that the LightGBM-LSTM hybrid model is best in terms of both accuracy and percentage difference on confirmed cases. This article uses two step of evaluating the performance of models one is accuracy from error another is using the percentage difference.

Number of Features Selected	CatBoost			XGBoost			LightGBM		
	MAPE	R ²	Accuracy	MAPE	R ²	Accuracy	MAPE	R ²	Accuracy
5	Bi-LSTM	1.20	0.62	98.8	1.86	0.14	8.69	<0	91.30
	GRU	1.70	0.33	98.3	1.04	0.67	6.07	<0	93.93
	LSTM	1.94	0.16	98.0	3.26	<0	6.68	<0	93.31
10	Bi-LSTM	2.11	0.16	97.89	9.63	<0	3.70	<0	96.30
	GRU	2.82	<0	97.17	7.45	<0	3.36	<0	96.63
	LSTM	1.75	0.3	98.2	8.62	<0	1.94	<0	98.05
15	Bi-LSTM	3.78	<0	96.21	9.90	<0	1.02	0.53	98.98
	GRU	3.77	<0	96.23	8.56	<0	1.06	0.45	98.94
	LSTM	2.80	<0	97.19	10.16	<0	0.87	0.66	99.13
20	Bi-LSTM	1.64	0.11	98.35	3.45	<0	1.96	0.23	98.04
	GRU	1.56	0.51	98.44	4.42	<0	1.61	0.43	98.39
	LSTM	1.16	0.12	98.84	6.27	<0	1.25	0.44	98.75
25	Bi-LSTM	2.86	<0	97.14	3.26	<0	3.62	<0	96.37
	GRU	1.63	<0	98.37	2.80	<0	1.41	<0	98.58
	LSTM	2.96	<0	97.04	2.93	<0	1.29	0.56	98.70

Table 5. Combinations of Models and their performance

Number of Features Selected	Prediction Models	Actual Cases	Feature Selection Algorithms					
			CatBoost		XGBoost		LightGBM	
			Predicted Cases	% Difference	Predicted Cases	% Difference	Predicted Cases	% Difference
5	Bi-LSTM	1577880.0	1743588.81	10.50	2484093.69	57.43	6773965.16	329.30
	GRU		1912173.95	21.18	1925286.04	22.01	5315702.67	236.88
	LSTM		1920854.69	21.73	3502554.67	121.97	5136501.48	225.53
10	Bi-LSTM		2247008.40	42.40	9281611.00	488.23	3076912.79	95.00
	GRU		2858846.98	81.18	7895010.88	400.35	3049435.76	93.26
	LSTM		1720396.66	9.03	8268197.43	424.00	1692402.87	7.26
15	Bi-LSTM		4170821.10	164.33	9884389.55	526.43	459162.91	70.90
	GRU		4182008.42	165.03	8818529.66	458.88	757986.52	51.96
	LSTM		3424435.92	117.02	10177234.63	544.99	1592105.35	0.90
20	Bi-LSTM		1371361.75	13.08	-2017312.98	227.84	2006764.18	27.18
	GRU		1825788.85	15.71	-1545271.17	197.93	2241837.54	42.07
	LSTM		962558.75	38.99	-3209539.45	303.40	1619605.35	2.64
25	Bi-LSTM		3824211.51	142.36	-1834150.49	216.24	3461569.54	119.38
	GRU		2079130.41	31.76	-369406.27	123.41	307963.19	80.48
	LSTM		640078.41	59.43	-1154947.52	173.19	1826978.06	15.78

Table 6. Combinations of Models and their percentage difference of Predicted cases

5. DISCUSSIONS & OBSERVATIONS

Overall, the comparison between these models involves evaluating each model's ability to perform well in its respective phase. The comparison helps to identify the strengths and weaknesses of each model and determine which model is best suited for this particular task of predicting the COVID-19 cases.

5.1. Short falls of Algorithm used in Feature Selection Phase on COVID-19 Data

5.1.1. XGBoost

The features selected by XGBoost are categorical in nature this is due to its nature of bias towards with high cardinality categorical features. XGBoost treats categorical features as numerical by assigning each unique category a unique integer label. This means that the model treats categories as ordered values, which may not be appropriate for high-cardinality categorical features where there is no natural ordering. Hence, the feature importance values for categorical features may be biased, as they may be influenced by the number of unique values assigned to each category.

5.1.2. CatBoost

CatBoost can handle categorical features by using an algorithm called ordered boosting. In ordered boosting, CatBoost orders the categorical feature values by their target mean values in the training set, and then uses the ordered values to split the data. However, this method of handling categorical features can also lead to more concentrated feature importance values on the most important categorical features.

5.2. Short falls of models used in Prediction Phase on COVID-19 Data

5.2.1. Bi-LSTM

Bi-LSTM has the most complex architecture when compared to the LSTM and GRU (i.e.) its bidirectional nature, which requires processing the input sequence in both forward and backward directions which may lead to the difficulty in processing the lengthier sequences of data. This made the Bi-LSTM to make the least predictions in these three models

5.2.2. GRU

GRU may not perform as well as LSTM on tasks that require precise control over the flow of information. May not be able to capture as much long-term context or long term dependencies as LSTM in very long sequences and may not be as good at capturing subtle patterns in the data. This leads to the lower accuracy in some of cases,

5.3. Proposed Methodology

Due to the shortfalls of the above algorithms and models in the pre-discussed phases, the LightGBM and LSTM prove to be the best hybrid model for predicting COVID-19 cases prediction. In addition, it is the model which gives the positive R^2 Score which is the right coefficient of determination and a very low MAPE of 0.87. When compared to the LSTM model which gives a MAPE of 2.07, the hybrid model performs better in terms of MAPE, R^2 and percentage difference between Actual and Predicted Cases. This is because the COVID-19 dataset is very large and prediction without the feature selection leads to lesser accuracy due to the features that are very ambiguous and repetitive. In such cases where there are larger datasets like COVID-19, the feature selection phase is necessary to extract a subset of the original dataset. By varying the LSTM units, batch size, optimizer and loss function, we can find the best performance in the prediction. The MAPE, R^2 and percentage difference are used to measure the accuracy of new patient count prediction. The predicted values help in taking the mitigation measures for the government authorities like preparation of oxygen cylinders, beds in hospitals, testing centers and vaccination doses. This would help in reducing the impact of COVID-19 cases and reducing the death rate. The time duration taken for training the network is from January 2020 to February 2022. The time duration taken for prediction and testing is from March 2022 to September 2022. The comparison between the actual patient count and the predicted patient count proves that the results from the hybrid model are more accurate and can be used in several other predictions also.

6. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, this study proposes a hybrid approach using LightGBM for feature selection and LSTM for COVID-19 cases prediction. The performance of the model is evaluated using MAPE and R^2 metrics, and the experimental results show that the hybrid model outperforms both LSTM and LightGBM models individually in terms of prediction accuracy. Also, evaluating the model's performance using the percentage difference enables the authorities to plan precise countermeasures. The selected features also provide insights into the most relevant factors for predicting COVID-19 cases, which can inform public health policy and resource allocation decisions. Additionally, the comparison of different models for the feature selection and prediction phase provides a comprehensive analysis of the performance of various machine learning algorithms in the context of COVID-19 cases prediction. The future work of our project includes the deaths count and trends in other countries.

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Declarations

Conflict of Interest

The author has no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the contents of the articles.

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